

INVESTIGATION OF NATURAL ADSORBENTS FOR DYE REMOVAL FROM TEXTILE WASTEWATER

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ABSTRACT

The release of untreated textile wastewater introduces intense coloration into natural water bodies, impacting aquatic ecosystems and water quality. This study examines the adsorption of methylene blue (MB) dye using two natural adsorbents: moringa seed powder and lemon seed powder. Parameters including contact time, adsorbent dose, pH, and initial dye concentration were optimized. Lemon seed achieved 86% removal at pH 7 in 30 minutes, outperforming moringa seed's 50% at pH 6 in 60 minutes. Adsorption data fit both Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms, indicating monolayer adsorption and favorable conditions. These low-cost, locally available materials present an eco-friendly alternative for dye removal.

Keywords: Textiles Wastewater, synthetic wastewater, methylene blue dye, adsorption, natural adsorbents, Moringa seeds, lemon seeds, adsorption isotherms

1. INTRODUCTION

Dyes are extensively employed across diverse industries such as textiles, rubber, plastics, printing, leather, cosmetics, and inks, generating large volumes of colored wastewater. Globally, over 7×10^5 tonnes of dyes are produced annually, with more than 10,000 commercially available varieties. Approximately 2% of these dyes are discharged as industrial effluents each year (Easton, 1995). Among all sectors, the textile industry is the largest consumer, accounting for over 107 kg of dye annually worldwide, of which about 90% adheres to textiles, while the remainder—over 1,000 tonnes—is released into wastewater streams (Robinson et al., 2001). The textile sector is one of India's oldest and most important industries, second only to agriculture in employment generation. Despite primarily using natural fibers, multiple chemicals and pigments are added during processing to achieve desired product characteristics. The industry consumes vast quantities of water, producing effluents with high color, Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), pH variations, turbidity, elevated temperature, and toxic contaminants. Direct discharge into water bodies severely impacts aquatic life, disrupts photosynthesis in aquatic plants, and degrades water aesthetics. The complex aromatic structures of dyes confer high stability against heat, light, microbial degradation, and oxidizing agents, making their removal challenging (Pearce et al., 2003). Exposure to

dyes can cause allergic reactions, skin irritation, cancer, genetic mutations, and other health hazards. The presence of visible color in water can also deter human and animal usage, making dye removal a priority in wastewater treatment. Dye removal methods are broadly categorized into chemical, biological, and physical processes (Elsagha et al., 2013). Selection depends on treatment cost, wastewater characteristics, and resource availability. Common physicochemical methods include adsorption, chemical oxidation, filtration, ion-exchange, coagulation/flocculation, reverse osmosis, and electro dialysis (Velmurugan et al., 2011). Adsorption has emerged as a favored technique due to low sludge generation, potential for sorbate recovery, use of established equipment, and low-cost regeneration (Kapdan & Kargi, 2002). Activated carbon is widely used owing to its high surface area, microporous structure, and surface reactivity. However, commercially available activated carbon is often expensive, as it is typically derived from non-renewable resources like coal. This limitation has driven interest in low-cost adsorbents derived from renewable natural or industrial by-products. Such waste materials are abundant, inexpensive, and environmentally sustainable (Geopaul, 1980). Numerous agricultural wastes have been investigated as alternative adsorbents for dye removal, including:

- Babassu coconut mesocarp (Vieira et al., 2009)
- Coconut husk (Jain & Shrivastava, 2008; Low & Lee, 1990; Gupta et al., 2010)
- Coconut shell fiber (de Sousa et al., 2010; Babel & Kurniawan, 2004)
- Coconut coir pith (Namasivayam et al., 2001)
- Coconut bunch waste (Hameed et al., 2008)
- Palm kernel fiber (El-Sayed, 2011)
- Rice husk (Gupta et al., 2006; Lakshmi et al., 2009)
- Sawdust (Batziias & Sidiras, 2007; Khattri & Singh, 2009)
- Peanut shell (Tanyildizi, 2011)
- Orange peels (Khaled et al., 2008; Arami et al., 2006)
- Waste tea leaves

The present research investigates inactivated lemon seed powder and Moringa seeds as low-cost, eco-friendly adsorbents for the removal of methylene blue (MB) from aqueous solutions. MB is a cationic dye widely used for silk, wood, and cotton coloring. It is toxic to both humans and animals—causing eye burns, respiratory distress (tachypnea, dyspnea), and gastrointestinal irritation, with potential for methemoglobinemia. Moringa seeds are sourced from overripe pods, while lemon seeds are collected from discarded citrus fruits in juice-processing facilities. Both are waste by-products with no significant economic value, making them promising sustainable adsorbents.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

Lemon seeds and oringa seeds were selected as low-cost, locally available adsorbents. Methylene blue (MB) dye ($C_{14}H_{18}N_3SCl$; molecular weight: 319.85 g/mol) was procured from a local supplier and used without further purification. pH adjustments were made using analytical-grade H_2SO_4 and NaOH. Double-distilled water was used throughout the experiments.

The instruments employed included an FTIR spectrophotometer (3000 Hyperion microscope with Vertex 80 FTIR system), UV–visible spectrophotometer (Spectroquant Pharo 300), mechanical shaker (20–880 rpm), analytical balance, pH meter-16, and sieves (300–600 μm).

2.2 Preparation of Adsorbent

Moringa seeds were collected from agricultural fields, and lemon seeds were obtained from a juice processing center. The seeds were washed thoroughly with distilled water, sun-dried for approximately one week, and ground using a domestic grinder. The powder was sieved to obtain particles between 450–600 μm, with adsorption experiments conducted using particles retained on the 600 μm sieve. The prepared powders were stored in airtight plastic containers and used without chemical activation or further treatment.

2.3 Preparation of Adsorbate

A stock solution of MB (1 g L⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g of dye in double-distilled water in a 1 L volumetric flask. Working solutions (5–50 mg L⁻¹) were obtained by serial dilution of the stock solution. A calibration curve for MB was established using these working concentrations.

Graph No.1: Calibration curve of methylene blue on spectrophotometer.

Batch Adsorption experiments

Batch adsorption experiments were conducted to optimize methylene blue (MB) removal from textile wastewater. MB solutions (10, 20, and 30 mg L⁻¹) were tested in 250 mL flasks containing 50 mL solution, agitated at 150 rpm. The effects of contact time (15–90 min at pH 6, 0.5 g adsorbent), adsorbent dose (0.1–0.8 g), pH (3–11, adjusted with 0.1 M HCl or H₂SO₄), and dye concentration (5–50 mg L⁻¹) were evaluated. After adsorption, samples were centrifuged (3000 rpm, 10–15 min) and analyzed using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer at λ_{max} = 651 nm. Adsorption capacity (q_e) was calculated using

$$q_e = \frac{V}{M}(C_e - C_0) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The percentage removal (R) was calculated using Eq. (2)

$$\%R = \frac{C_e - C_0}{C_0} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, C₀ and C_e are the initial and equilibrium MB concentrations respectively (mg L⁻¹), V is the MB solution volume (L) and m is the mass of the adsorbent (g). The equilibrium data were evaluated using the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm and characteristic parameters for both isotherms were determined.

Spectral analysis

An FTIR spectrophotometer (3000 Hyperion Microscope with Vertex 80 FTIR System) was used to record the spectra of lemon seed powder and moringa seed powder in the 4500–500 cm⁻¹ range. The IR graph's bands and stretch vibrations indicate that both samples include a variety of functional groups, including hydroxyl, aromatic, aliphatic, and carboxylic acid groups. Every peak exhibits a shift to a new wavelength, indicating that the functional groups are involved in the methylene blue adsorption process.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of adsorbents on the removal capacity of methylene blue dye was compared. Batch experimentation served as the foundation for this. Adsorption was examined in relation to starting dye concentration, duration, pH, and adsorbent quantity. At a starting concentration of 20 mg/l, the adsorbent's ability to remove color is compared.

Effect of time

Experiments at 10, 20, and 30 mg L⁻¹ MB concentrations (pH 6) showed that dye removal was rapid initially, followed by slower adsorption until equilibrium. For moringa seed powder, maximum removal occurred at 60, 60, and 75 min for 10, 20, and 30 mg L⁻¹, with efficiencies of 75%, 50.6%, and 38.34%, respectively. Lemon seed powder achieved peak removal at 45 min (10 mg L⁻¹) and 30 min (20 and 30 mg L⁻¹), with efficiencies of 94.5%, 86%, and 82.33%, respectively. Lemon seed powder consistently outperformed moringa seed powder, achieving higher removal efficiencies in shorter contact times

Graph No.2 Comparative results for efficiency of both adsorbents with respect to time

Effect of Adsorbent dose

Adsorbent dosage plays a key role in determining removal efficiency for a given initial dye concentration. For all three concentrations tested, increasing dosage improved dye removal until an optimum point, after which adsorption slowed or reached equilibrium—likely due to site overlap/aggregation, which reduces the effective surface area and lengthens the diffusion path. Moringa seed powder achieved peak efficiency of 50.6% at 0.4 g in 60 min, whereas lemon seed powder reached 84.5% efficiency at 0.5 g in 30 min. Although moringa seeds peaked at a lower dose, lemon seeds showed significantly higher overall removal performance. Beyond the optimum dosage, adsorption declined for both adsorbents.

Graph No.3: Comparative results for efficiency of both adsorbents with respect to adsorbent dose.

Effect of pH

pH is a critical parameter in dye adsorption, as it influences both the ionization of dye molecules and the surface charge of the adsorbent, thereby affecting electrostatic interactions. Color removal by moringa seed powder was tested across pH 3–11 using 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M H₂SO₄ for adjustment. Lower adsorption at acidic pH was attributed to competition between excess H⁺ ions and cationic dye molecules. As pH increased, more negatively charged sites formed on the adsorbent surface, enhancing cationic dye uptake via electrostatic attraction. Variations in adsorption within this range suggest that chemical interactions also contribute alongside electrostatic effects. Both adsorbents performed best near neutral pH: moringa seed powder achieved 50.8% removal at pH 6, while lemon seed powder reached 87% at pH 7, indicating superior performance of lemon seeds in mildly alkaline conditions.

Graph No.4: Comparative results for efficiency of both adsorbents with respect to pH

Effect of initial dye concentration

The initial dye concentration strongly influences removal efficiency due to the relationship between available adsorption sites and the number of dye molecules in solution. Generally, higher initial concentrations lead to reduced removal percentages, as adsorption sites become saturated despite increased total uptake. At lower concentrations, the ratio of dye molecules to active sites is low, making fractional adsorption largely independent of starting concentration. Experimental results show that removal efficiency for both adsorbents decreases with increasing initial concentration. At 5 mg/L, maximum efficiencies were 94% for lemon seed powder and 92% for moringa seed powder. At 50 mg/L, efficiencies declined to 82% and 35.6%, respectively, indicating that lemon seed powder maintains higher performance across all tested concentrations

Graph No.5: Comparative results for efficiency of both adsorbents with respect to initial dye concentration

Adsorption isotherm

Important models for describing adsorption behavior are provided by adsorption isotherms. It provides an understanding of the nature and mechanism of the adsorption process as well as the interactions between the adsorbent and the adsorbate. To determine the adsorption capacity of different adsorbents, it is important to examine isotherm data. Two equilibrium isotherms were examined in order to study the adsorption isotherm: Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms are used to fit experimental data in adsorption studies in order to determine the degree and amount of favorability of adsorption. The Langmuir model was created under the presumption that the adsorbate species would form a monolayer on the adsorbent's surface. In order to assess the adsorbent's adsorption effectiveness, the Langmuir isotherm must be studied. Enhancing the operating conditions for efficient adsorption is another benefit of this study. The graph below displays the plots of $1/q_e$ against $1/C_e$ for both adsorbents. Plotting of the experimental data resulted in an equation that was compared to the $y = mx + c$ equation. R^2 , K_L , and q_{max} are calculated using the graph values and are shown in Table No. 1. The system fits the isotherm, as shown by the graph's formation of a straight line. Below is the Langmuir equation.

$$q_e = \frac{q_{max} K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

This can be linearized to

$$\frac{1}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_{max} K_L C_e} + \frac{1}{q_{max}} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where, C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L), q_e is the amount of dye adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g), q_{max} is the theoretical maximum adsorption capacity ($mg\ g^{-1}$), K_L is the Langmuir isotherm constant ($L\ mg^{-1}$).

Graph No.6: Graphical Representation of Langmuir Isotherm for moringa seed powder.

Graph No.7: Graphical Representation of Langmuir Isotherm for lemon seed powder.

Table no.1: Langmuir Constants for various adsorbents

Adsorbent	Langmuir Constant		
	Q _{max}	KL	R2
Moringa seed	2.351	0.12	0.9754
Lemon seed	2.9788	0.273	0.868

When designing adsorption systems, the equilibrium adsorption isotherms are crucial. The Freundlich isotherm may provide adequate equilibrium adsorption data. The equation for Freundlich is provided as

$$q_e = K_f C_e^{1/n} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg L^{-1}), K_f is the Freundlich adsorption constant associated with the adsorbent's adsorption capacity, n is a dimensionless constant that can be used to explain the extent of adsorption and the adsorption intensity between the solute concentration and adsorbent, and q_e is the amount of dye adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g). The Freundlich equation's linear form is typically written as

$$\log_e q_e = \log_e K_f + (1/n) \log_e C_e \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Graph no.8: Graphical Representation of Freundlich Isotherm for moringa seed powder

Graph No.9: Graphical Representation of Freundlich Isotherm for lemon seed powder.

Graphs 8 and 9 depict the plots of $\log Q_e$ versus $\log C_e$, where the slope (m) and intercept (c) obtained from the straight-line fit were compared to the general equation $y = mx + c$. A linear relationship confirmed the applicability of the Freundlich isotherm model. Using the derived parameters, the values in Table 2 were calculated, and the correlation coefficient (R) indicated a favorable adsorption process for both adsorbents. These results reaffirm that, under the experimental conditions, both the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models adequately describe the adsorption of methylene blue (MB) onto natural adsorbents.

Table No.2: Freundlich Constants for various adsorbents

Adsorbent	Freundlich Constant		
	1/n	K_f	R^2
Moringa seed	0.3839	0.53272	0.9555
Lemon seed	0.3193	1.0353	0.9313

The value of R indicates the type of the isotherm. If $R > 1$ isotherm is unfavorable, If $R = 1$ isotherm is Linear, if $0 < R < 1$ isotherm is Favorable or if $R < 0$ isotherm is Irreversible.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that powdered moringa and lemon seeds can effectively remove methylene blue (MB) dye from aqueous solutions, with dye molecules binding strongly to the adsorbent surfaces. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy confirmed the presence of functional groups in both adsorbents that contribute to adsorption. Comparative analysis revealed that lemon seed powder is a significantly more effective natural adsorbent than moringa seed powder, achieving a maximum removal efficiency of 86% at room temperature, compared to approximately 50% for moringa seed powder. The optimal pH for moringa seed powder was found to be 6, while lemon seed powder performed best at pH 7. For both materials, removal efficiency stabilized or slightly declined at pH values above 7. Isotherm studies indicated that lemon seed powder, even under nominal treatment, exhibited superior adsorption performance compared to moringa seed powder. The strong linear correlation coefficients obtained suggest that adsorption parameters derived from Langmuir–Freundlich isotherms effectively describe the underlying adsorption mechanisms..

5. REFERENCES

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